

ARCHITECTURE

INFLUENCE OF GROWING ELEMENTS ON SPRING BARLEY PRODUCTIVITY IN THE NORTHERN STEPPE OF UKRAINE

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Abstract

This article considers the technological scheme of growing spring barley of different varieties (variety Hermes and variety Avatar) with the use of bacterial preparation Biocomplex-BTU-r as a seed treatment and foliar feeding against the background of complex mineral fertilizer $N_{45}P_{45}K_{30}$ with the use of siderate (white mustard) and stubble destructor EcoStern (2 l/ha) in a tank mixture with 50 kg/ha of urea. In scientific research the influence of different combination of variants on biometric indicators of crop plants, yield and its structure was studied. The maximum above-mentioned indicators were exactly when using seed treatment with bacterial preparation, its use in the treatment of plants during vegetation, application of complex mineral fertilizers, sowing of a sideral crop with its treatment with stubble destructor with urea. In this case, the yield of varieties Hermes and Avatar were 4.84 and 5.13 tons / ha respectively.

Keywords: barley, biopreparation, mineral fertilizers, siderate, stubble destructor, plant height, yield structure, yield.

Introduction

Growing modern agricultural products while improving soil fertility and providing crops with fertilizers and water regime is one of the main goals in Ukraine. It is necessary to develop and implement new adaptive, biological and varietal methods of growing grain crops that would maximize the biological potential of the variety and local natural conditions of the Southern Steppe [1-4]. Increasing the yield and improving the quality of seeds of these crops can only be substantiated by a thorough analysis of bioorganic and agronomic measures of the technology.

The improvement of current and development of domestic scientific and technological measures, new varieties, microbial strains for seed treatment, spraying of crops with growth-regulating preparations of microbial origin in combination with the incorporation of green manure into the soil, and other factors are important prerequisites for the study of adaptive varietal technologies for growing grain crops. This pairing will help spring wheat and spring barley products remain competitive on both domestic and international markets [5-10].

The fact that biological goods are based on microorganisms isolated from natural biocenoses, do not harm the environment, and are safe for both humans and animals is one of the main reasons for their practical interest. The method of biological farming frequently employs seed treatment with multipurpose bacterial preparations that can have a positive impact on plant physiological processes and, as a result, help to increase crop output. The production of antibiotic compounds and improved nitrogen and phosphorus feeding are all benefits of bacterial preparations based on nitrogen-fixing and phosphorus-mobilizing microorganisms. Because microbial preparations don't harm the environment, have a strong selection effect, are simple

to apply, and have endless resources for growth, the biological technique is safe for people and warm-blooded animals [9-14].

Due to the evidence supporting the peculiarities of plant growth and development, the combination of green manure fertilizer, nitrogen-fixing and phosphorus-mobilizing activity, photosynthetic and net productivity of crops, and the development and application of adaptive, biological, and varietal technologies for their cultivation in the South, researchers have been looking for ways to create highly productive plant-rybizobial systems that would significantly increase productivity.

Frequent weather fluctuations are a defining feature of Ukraine's climate, as well as a significant number of unfavorable phenomena for agriculture. Extreme weather conditions (abnormally hot or cold) have become more common at different stages of plant organogenesis, which has a very negative impact on the quantity and quality of crops grown.

Although the climate of the Southern Steppe's insufficiently moist zone is generally suitable for growing grain crops, there have been significant fluctuations in hydrothermal parameters recently compared to the average annual data.

Our research looked at the impact of the bacterial preparation Biocomplex-BTU-r on seed treatment and foliar feeding in spring barley with various varietal compositions against the backdrop of mineral fertilizers and green manure culture.

In our research, we studied the effect of the bacterial preparation Biocomplex-BTU-r during seed treatment and foliar feeding of spring barley of different varietal composition against the background of mineral fertilizers and green manure culture using a stubble biodestructor.

Materials and methods. The experiments were conducted in 2020-2021 on the basis of the experimental field of the Educational and Research Center of Mykolaiv National Agrarian University. The soils of the experimental farm are represented by southern low-humus, slightly saline, heavy loamy chernozem on loess. The soil profile of the experimental field is represented by the following arrangement of horizons [10, 15-22].

The lowest moisture capacity of 0-70 cm of the soil layer is 22.0%, the wilting moisture content is 9.7% of the dry soil mass, and the density of the soil is 1.40 g/cm. The content of humus in the topsoil is 2.9-3.2%, mobile phosphorus is 38%, and exchangeable potassium is 332-525 mg/kg of soil. The soil contains 0.20-0.25% of gross nitrogen and 0.12-0.14% of phosphorus. The soil absorbing complex is saturated mainly with calcium and magnesium. The reaction of the soil solution of the upper horizons is close to neutral or slightly alkaline (pH = 6.8-7.2), increasing down the profile. By its characteristics, the soil of the experimental field is typical for the chernozem of the southern steppe zone of Ukraine and is suitable for growing most of the main field crops. The humus horizon of 47-52 cm is dark gray with a chestnut tint, characterized by salinity and a narrow ratio of Ca^{2+*} and Mg^{2+} (2.5-2.8) [7, 10, 15-22].

The scheme of the experiment to study the productivity of spring barley varieties included the following options:

I. Factor A (fertilization).

1. No fertilizer (control);
2. $N_{45}P_{45}K_{30}$;
3. $N_{45}P_{45}K_{30}$ + green manure + stubble destructor EcoStern + 50 kg/ha urea.

II. Factor B (seed treatment)

1. Water treatment (control);
2. Biocomplex BTU-r (1.0 l/t).

III. Factor C (foliar feeding)

1. No treatment;
2. Biocomplex-BTU-r (0.8 l/ha)

The total area of the plot is 36 m². The registered area of the plot is 25 m². The placement of options is systematic.

Spring barley agrotechnics in the experiment was generally accepted for the growing zone. Crops were treated with the biological product Biocomplex-BTU-r (0.8 l/ha) at the end of tillering together with the application of the herbicide Granstar Pro (25 g/ha). Spraying with Abacus fungicide (1.6 l/ha) was carried out during the flag leaf period of the crop.

The predecessor of spring barley in the experiment was winter wheat with grinding of post-harvest plant

residues of 5.0 t/ha and minimum incorporation into the soil to a depth of 5-6 cm, followed by sowing of white mustard for green manure (according to the scheme of the experiment) and incorporation of green fertilizer into the soil to a depth of 20-22 cm. Before plowing, the stubble destructor EcoStern was applied at a rate of 2.0 l/ha with 50 kg of urea and with a working fluid outflow of 300 l/ha. Early spring pre-sowing soil tillage for sowing the crop after early spring harrowing was carried out to the depth of sowing (5-7 cm). Sowing was carried out with a SZ 3.6 seeder with subsequent rolling of the crop with a 3KKSH-6 ring-spur roller.

Phenological observations were carried out throughout the growing season (according to the methodology of state variety testing of agricultural crops, 2000) [23].

The number of plants was counted in 2 periods: after full germination and during the harvesting period in all variants in 2 replications. The height was counted and measured on 2 rows of 1 running meter in three places of each variant on fixed sites [24].

Before harvesting, sheaves were selected with roots in I-III replications to determine the structure of the crop.

The grain harvest was recorded by continuous harvesting with a Sampo-300 combine harvester and weighing from each plot.

The mathematical processing of the results was carried out by the method of analysis of variance according to B.O. Dospekhov [25].

Research results. According to the results of our research, on average, bacterization of spring barley seeds and treatment of crops with Biocomplex-BTU-r with the simultaneous use of a stubble biodestructor and green manure fertilizer had a positive effect on the growth and development of plants of both barley varieties. Seed treatment had a slight effect on the plant density at the germination stage, but had a significant impact on productive tillering, or stem density.

Because of this, the experimental variants differed most in stem density, which had the greatest impact on other agricultural productivity parameters.

The height of the stems of the Hermes variety, depending on the treatment of seeds and crops with biological products, as well as fertilization, exceeded the control ones by 3.2-13.7 cm, increasing from 64.6 cm in the control to 78.3 cm in the variant of seed treatment and sowing with the biological product of polyfunctional action Biocomplex-BTU-r against the background of $N_{45}P_{45}K_{30}$ + green manure + EcoStern + Urea (Table 1).

Table 1

Influence of the studied factors on the indicators of structural elements of the crop and quality of spring barley seeds of Hermes variety (average for 2020-2021)

Seed treatment (Factor B)	Number of productive stems, pieces/m ²	Length of stems, cm	Coefficient of productive tillering	Number of grains per ear, pieces	Weight of 1000 grains, g	Grain weight, g
No treatment (Factor C)						
No fertilizer (control) (Factor A)						
Water treatment (control)	378,5	64,6	1,58	19,8	44,3	638
Biocomplex BTU- r	411,1	68,1	1,68	20,8	44,9	649
N ₄₅ P ₄₅ K ₃₀ (Factor A)						
Water treatment (control)	426,0	71,4	1,75	20,4	46,6	645
Biocomplex BTU- r	442,6	73,5	1,79	21,2	47,0	654
N ₄₅ P ₄₅ K ₃₀ + green manure + stubble destructor EcoStern + 50 kg/ha urea (Factor A)						
Water treatment (control)	455,5	72,2	1,86	20,7	47,2	656
Biocomplex BTU- r	464,3	75,4	1,87	21,4	47,5	663
Biocomplex-BTU-r (Factor C)						
No fertilizer (control) (Factor A)						
Water treatment (control)	396,3	67,8	1,65	20,2	45,1	642
Biocomplex BTU- r	424,0	69,7	1,73	21,0	45,8	651
N ₄₅ P ₄₅ K ₃₀ (Factor A)						
Water treatment (control)	440,6	74,9	1,81	21,0	46,8	647
Biocomplex BTU- r	442,2	77,1	1,84	21,8	47,2	655
N ₄₅ P ₄₅ K ₃₀ + green manure + stubble destructor EcoStern + 50 kg/ha urea (Factor A)						
Water treatment (control)	459,2	75,7	1,87	21,5	47,1	658
Biocomplex BTU- r	460,1	78,3	1,88	22,1	47,6	664

It was found that the inoculation of barley seeds of the Hermes variety with microbial preparations on average over the years had a slight effect on the number of grains in the ear. Thus, against the background of natural soil fertility, the number of grains from seed treatment increased only from 20.8 to 21.4 grains per ear. At the same time, spraying of crops with the bacterial preparation Biocomplex-BTU-r on the background without fertilizers formed 21 pcs. grains in the ear of the crop.

The maximum number of grains in the ear of spring barley plants of the Hermes variety on average for 2020-2021 (22.1 pcs.) was obtained in the variant of crop cultivation under the treatment of seeds with the biological product Biocomplex-BTU-r, the introduction of N₄₅P₄₅K₃₀ + green manure + EcoStern + Urea and foliar feeding of crops with a bacterial preparation.

The weight of 1000 seeds of barley variety Hermes from seed treatment also increased slightly in variants without fertilizers (from 44.3 g to 45.1 g without treatment of crops and from 44.9 g to 45.8 g - when spraying with Biocomplex-BTU-r). Against the background of N₄₅P₄₅K₃₀ and N₄₅P₄₅K₃₀ with green manure, this indicator increased, when treating seeds with the preparation, it was 47.0-47.6 g, and under control (water treatment) - 46.6-47.1 g.

Such an indicator as grain nature in the Hermes variety slightly increased with the use of fertilizers and treatment of seeds and crops with the biological product, ranging from 638 g in the variant without treatment of seeds and crops to 664 g in the background of N₄₅P₄₅K₃₀ + green manure + EcoStern + Urea with treatment of crops and seeds with the Biocomplex-BTU-r preparation.

The beginning of the phenological phases (from tillering to milky ripeness) in the areas where fertilizers were applied was observed 2-3 days later than in the background of natural soil fertility. Barley seed ripening occurred first in unfertilized areas, where plants continued to grow for another 4-6 days in the Hermes variety and for 5-8 days in the Avatar variety (due to the latter's greater resistance to leaf diseases).

Structural analysis of Avatar plants showed that the number of productive stems, their height, productive tillering coefficient and the number of grains per ear significantly increased after seed treatment with the studied preparation, although not as much as after fertilization (Table 2).

Thus, the number of stems per 1 m² in the control variant of seed treatment (water moistening) ranged

from 360.0 pcs. against the background of natural fertility to 435.8 pcs. when N₄₅P₄₅K₃₀ was applied with green manure, stubble biodestructor, urea and seeds and crops were treated with the complex action preparation Biocomplex-BTU-r. When applying the preparation, the sowing density increased, according to the background, from 396.0 to 435.8 seeds per 1 m².

Depending on the factor studied in the experiment, the stem length of the Avatar variety ranged from 63.8 cm in the variant without treatment with bacterial preparations and fertilizers to 77.8 cm when seeds and crops were treated with Biocomplex-BTU-r against the background of N₄₅P₄₅K₃₀ + green manure + EcoStern + Urea. The coefficient of productive tillering for the same variants, respectively, increased from 1.50 to 1.76 stems per plant, and the number of grains - from 20.3 to 22.9 per ear.

Table 2

Influence of the studied factors on the indicators of structural elements of the crop and quality of spring barley seeds of Avatar variety (average for 2020-2021)

Seed treatment (Factor B)	Number of productive stems, pieces/m ²	Length of stems, cm	Coefficient of productive tillering	Number of grains per ear, pieces	Weight of 1000 grains, g	Grain weight, g
No treatment (Factor C)						
No fertilizer (control) (Factor A)						
Water treatment (control)	360,0	63,8	1,50	20,3	47,7	642
Biocomplex BTU- r	396,0	67,5	1,62	21,1	48,1	658
N ₄₅ P ₄₅ K ₃₀ (Factor A)						
Water treatment (control)	399,6	70,5	1,64	21,5	50,4	653
	420,8	72,7	1,70	21,9	51,0	665
N ₄₅ P ₄₅ K ₃₀ + green manure + stubble destructor EcoStern + 50 kg/ha urea (Factor A)						
Water treatment (control)	413,8	71,9	1,69	22,4	50,6	657
Biocomplex BTU- r	422,4	75,2	1,71	22,8	51,3	671
Biocomplex-BTU-r (Factor C)						
No fertilizer (control) (Factor A)						
Water treatment (control)	386,9	66,4	1,61	20,6	48,3	644
Biocomplex BTU- r	402,7	68,8	1,65	21,3	48,5	661
N ₄₅ P ₄₅ K ₃₀ (Factor A)						
Water treatment (control)	422,6	73,6	1,74	21,7	50,6	652
Biocomplex BTU- r	433,9	76,4	1,76	22,1	51,1	667
N ₄₅ P ₄₅ K ₃₀ + green manure + stubble destructor EcoStern + 50 kg/ha urea (Factor A)						
Water treatment (control)	428,5	74,9	1,75	22,6	50,8	664
Biocomplex BTU- r	435,8	77,8	1,76	22,9	51,4	677

The weight of 1000 grains in this variety was more influenced by fertilizer, when seeds were treated with bacteria from Biocomplex-BTU-r on backgrounds with fertilizer and the use of green manure, this indicator increased from 47.7 g under water treatment in the control to 51.4 g in the best variant. The use of the whole complex of the studied variants gave the maximum weight of 1000 grains (51.4 g).

The grain weight also increased when treating seeds of this variety with Biocomplex-BTU-r against the background of $N_{45}P_{45}K_{30}$ + green manure + EcoStern + Urea - up to 642-677 g and relatively 642 g against the background of natural fertility.

The main criterion for assessing the effectiveness of various measures to improve barley growing conditions is their impact on yield. On average, over the years of research, pre-sowing seed treatment and spraying of crops with bacterial preparations of Hermes and Avatar varieties against the background of green manure application significantly increased crop yields. The highest yields were obtained in the variants of seed and crop treatment of both varieties with the polyfunctional preparation Biocomplex-BTU-r against the background of $N_{45}P_{45}K_{30}$ + green manure + EcoStern + 50 kg/ha of urea, which amounted to 4.84 t/ha in Hermes variety and 5.13 t/ha in Avatar variety (Table 3).

Table 3

Yield of spring barley variety Hermes depending on the studied factors (average for 2020-2021)

Seed treatment (Factor B)	Yield by repetitions, t/ha				Yield deviations					
					Factor A		Factor B		Factor C	
	I	II	III	average	t/ha	%	t/ha	%	t/ha	%
No treatment (Factor C)										
No fertilizer (control) (Factor A)										
Water treatment (control)	3,24	3,35	3,37	3,32	K	-	K	-	K	-
Biocomplex BTU- r	3,76	3,90	3,87	3,84	0,52	15,7	K	-	K	-
$N_{45}P_{45}K_{30}$ (Factor A)										
Water treatment (control)	3,98	4,06	4,11	4,05	K	-	0,73	22,0	K	-
Biocomplex BTU- r	4,36	4,41	4,47	4,41	0,36	8,9	0,57	14,8	K	-
$N_{45}P_{45}K_{30}$ + green manure + stubble destructor EcoStern + 50 kg/ha urea (Factor A)										
Water treatment (control)	4,42	4,38	4,55	4,45	K	-	1,13	34,0	K	-
Biocomplex BTU- r	4,60	4,72	4,84	4,72	0,27	6,1	0,88	22,9	K	-
Biocomplex-BTU-r (Factor C)										
No fertilizer (control) (Factor A)										
Water treatment (control)	3,50	3,71	3,62	3,61	K	-	K	-	0,29	8,7
Biocomplex BTU- r	3,92	4,15	4,17	4,08	0,47	13,0	K	-	0,24	6,3
$N_{45}P_{45}K_{30}$ (Factor A)										
Water treatment (control)	4,25	4,34	4,41	4,33	K	-	0,72	19,9	0,28	6,9
Biocomplex BTU- r	4,45	4,62	4,58	4,55	0,22	5,1	0,47	11,5	0,14	3,2
$N_{45}P_{45}K_{30}$ + green manure + stubble destructor EcoStern + 50 kg/ha urea (Factor A)										
Water treatment (control)	4,53	4,77	4,65	4,65	K	-	1,04	28,8	0,20	4,5
Biocomplex BTU- r	4,92	4,78	4,83	4,84	0,19	4,1	0,76	18,6	0,12	2,5

The variant of seed treatment of Hermes variety with Biocomplex-BTU-r, depending on the fertilizer background and the presence of crops treated with it, provided an increase in grain yield compared to the control - 0.19-0.52 t/ha or 4.1-15.7%. At the same time, the percentage of increase from seed treatment with the bacterial preparation significantly decreased in the background with fertilizers (6.1-8.9% vs. 13.0-15.7% in the background without fertilizers), and even more in the background with fertilizers and treatment of crops with Biocomplex-BTU-r (4.1-5.1% increase compared to the background without spraying).

The yield increase of the Hermes variety from the use of fertilizer at the rate of $N_{45}P_{45}K_{30}$ was 0.57 - 0.73 t/ha and 0.88 - 1.13 t/ha - against the background of $N_{45}P_{45}K_{30}$ + green manure + EcoStern + Urea. Another 0.47 to 1.04 t/ha or 11.5 - 28.8% (depending on fertilization and seed treatment) was obtained from spraying crops with Biocomplex-BTU-r in the phase of the beginning of tubing of the crop.

Weakening of the effect of microbial preparations for seed treatment was noted due to improvement of the general agro background. Thus, it was found that when treating Hermes seeds with a microbial preparation, the percentage increase in yield on the background without fertilizers was (relative to the variant without seed treatment) 15.7%, while on the background of fertilizer $N_{45}P_{45}K_{30}$ - 8.9%, and on the background of $N_{45}P_{45}K_{30}$ + green manure + EcoStern + Urea - 6.1%. At the same time, against the background of treatment of crops with Biocomplex-BTU-r, the effect on yield was further reduced. As an assumption, it can be pointed out that these biological products act as stimulants, which are more effective under stressful conditions (in particular, lack of fertilizers) than under optimal crop growing conditions.

Analysis of the yield data of Avatar variety shows that the effectiveness of seed treatment of this variety with the studied preparations is even more reduced on a fertilized background and under sowing treatment than in Hermes variety (Table 4).

Table 4

Yield of spring barley variety Avatar depending on the studied factors (average for 2020-2021)

Seed treatment (Factor B)	Yield by repetitions, t/ha				Yield deviations					
					Factor A		Factor B		Factor C	
	I	II	III	average	t/ha	%	t/ha	%	t/ha	%
No treatment (Factor C)										
No fertilizer (control) (Factor A)										
Water treatment (control)	3,41	3,50	3,55	3,49	K	-	K	-	K	-
Biocomplex BTU- r	3,83	3,97	4,02	3,94	0,45	12,9	K	-	K	-
N ₄₅ P ₄₅ K ₃₀ (Factor A)										
Water treatment (control)	4,23	4,37	4,39	4,33	K	-	0,84	24,1	K	-
Biocomplex BTU- r	4,55	4,76	4,79	4,70	0,37	8,5	0,76	19,3	K	-
N ₄₅ P ₄₅ K ₃₀ + green manure + stubble destructor EcoStern + 50 kg/ha urea (Factor A)										
Water treatment (control)	4,54	4,70	4,83	4,69	K	-	1,20	34,4	K	-
Biocomplex BTU- r	4,98	4,90	4,95	4,94	0,25	5,3	1,00	25,4	K	-
Biocomplex-BTU-r (Factor C)										
No fertilizer (control) (Factor A)										
Water treatment (control)	3,76	3,90	3,89	3,85	K	-	K	-	0,36	10,3
Biocomplex BTU- r	4,02	4,19	4,27	4,16	0,31	8,1	K	-	0,22	5,6
N ₄₅ P ₄₅ K ₃₀ (Factor A)										
Water treatment (control)	4,52	4,65	4,74	4,64	K	-	0,79	20,5	0,31	7,2
Biocomplex BTU- r	4,83	4,87	5,00	4,90	0,26	5,6	0,74	17,8	0,20	4,3
N ₄₅ P ₄₅ K ₃₀ + green manure + stubble destructor EcoStern + 50 kg/ha urea (Factor A)										
Water treatment (control)	4,81	4,96	4,99	4,92	K	-	1,07	27,8	0,23	4,9
Biocomplex BTU- r	5,03	5,15	5,21	5,13	0,21	4,3	0,97	23,3	0,19	3,8

Thus, the greatest increase in yield (12.9%) was observed in the variant of seed treatment with Biocomplex-BTU-r on the background without fertilizers and without spraying the crops with it. However, the highest yield of this variety was obtained from the plots of the variant of seed treatment and sowing with Biocomplex-BTU-r on the background of fertilizer N₄₅P₄₅K₃₀ + green manure + EcoStern + Urea and amounted to 5.13 t/ha, while in the variant without fertilizers and without treatment of seeds and crops with biological products it was 3.49 t/ha.

When Avatar seeds were treated with Biocomplex-BTU-r, the increase in grain yield, depending on the fertilizer background and the presence of crop treatment, was 0.21-0.45 t/ha or 4.3-12.9% compared to the control.

Fertilizer application at the rate of N₄₅P₄₅K₃₀ increased the yield from plots without seed treatment by 0.72 - 0.73 t/ha or 19.9 - 22.0%, and on the background of N₄₅P₄₅K₃₀ + green manure + EcoStern + Urea - by 1.04 - 1.13 t/ha or 28.8 - 34.0%. The fairly high barley yields against the background of natural soil fertility can be explained by good agro background and favorable weather conditions.

Conclusions. Thus, as a result of our research, we found different sensitivity of spring barley varieties Hermes and Avatar to the use of seed inoculation and spraying of crops with Biocomplex-BTU-r and the background of mineral fertilizers and green manure. The highest crop yield was obtained in the variant of treatment of seeds and crops of both varieties with the polyfunctional preparation Biocomplex-BTU-r against the background of N₄₅P₄₅K₃₀ + green manure + EcoStern + Urea, which amounted to 4.84 t/ha in the Hermes variety and 5.13 t/ha in the Avatar variety. This

variant had the best conditions for the growth of biometric parameters and crop structure as a component of the research results.

References

1. Kaminskyi V.F., Sayko V.F. Agriculture of the XXI century. Problems and solutions. Interdepartmental scientific collection "Agriculture". K.: Publishing house. "Edelweiss. 2015. № 2(89). P. 3-11.
2. Sychevskyi M.P. Formation of the national food system on the basis of independence. Bulletin of Agrarian Science. 2014. № 6. P. 11-18.
3. Boyko PI Organic crop rotation. Agroexpert. 2015. № 6 (83). P. 26-29.
4. Copyright certificate No 78446. Application of innovative complex technologies of nutrition of field crops in crop rotations of the Steppe zone of Ukraine" for 2017: a literary and written work of scientific and technical nature / V. V. Gamayunov et al.
5. Petrychenko V. F., Tikhonovych I. A., Kots S. Y. et al. Agricultural microbiology and balanced development of agrosystems. Bulletin of Agrarian Science. 2012. No. 8. P. 5-11.
6. Derevianskyi VP, Vasyuk O., Malynovska I. Efficiency of biological preparations and microelements in the technology of spring wheat cultivation. Interdepartmental thematic scientific collection Agricultural Microbiology. 2013. № 17. P. 111-118.
7. Kovalenko OA, Korkhova MM, Khomenko AK Application of soil and endophytic microorganisms in the use of green manure crops for spring barley cultivation in the Steppe zone of Ukraine. World plant resources: state and prospects of development: materials of the V International scientific-practical conference, Kyiv, June 7, 2019 / Ministry of Agrarian Policy and Food of Ukraine; Ukrainian Institute of Expertise.

Ukraine; Ukrainian Institute of Plant Variety Expertise, 2019. P.193-195.

8. Method for the use of biological products in the cultivation of winter barley: patent for utility model UA129161 : A01C1/08 (2006.01) No 129169. applied for 10.04.2018; published 25.10.2018, Bulletin. No 20.

9. Microbial preparations in agriculture. Theory and practice: Monograph / [V.V. Volkohon, O.V. Nadkernychna, T.M. Kovalevska, et al. edited by V.V. Volkohon. K.: Agrarian Science, 2006. 312 p.

10. Agroecological substantiation and development of elements of biologized technologies for growing crops in the South of Ukraine: Doctor of Agricultural Sciences: 06.01.09 / Kovalenko Oleh Anatoliiovych. Kherson, 2021. 592 p.

11. Bunyak N., Volkohon V. Microbial preparations for agricultural crops. Agrarian Week. Ukraine. URL: <https://a7d.com.ua/analytika/tehnology/13835-mkrobn-preparati-dlya-slskogospodarskih-kultur.html> (accessed 12.07.2023).

12. Sytnikov D.M. Biotechnology of nitrogen-fixing microorganisms and prospects for the use of preparations based on them. Biotechnologiya. 2012. T. 5. P. 4-45.

13. Naydenova O. Biological products and fertility. Microbiological preparations can increase the efficiency of organic farming, it is only necessary to choose the right one for a particular crop. The Ukrainian FARMER. 2013. No 10. P. 34-36.

14. Kovalenko O. A., Kindylevych A. D., Fedyuk V. I. Influence of growth regulating substances on the productivity of spring barley during cultivation in the farm "Ajax" of Veselinovsky district of Mykolaiv region. Participation of young people in the development of the agro-industrial complex of the country: materials of the 28th student scientific-theoretical conference, Mykolaiv, March 23-25. 2016p. Mykolaiv: MNAU, 2016. P. 37-39.

15. Kovalenko OA, Fedorchuk MI, Neroda RS, Donets YL Sunflower cultivation with the use of microfertilizers and bacterial preparations. Bulletin of Poltava State Agrarian Academy. 2020. № 2. P. 111-134. <https://doi.org/10.31210/visnyk2020.02.02> (accessed 07.09.2021)

16. Kovalenko O.A., Melnikova K. V. Influence of biological products on the productivity of winter wheat in the southern steppe of Ukraine. Proceedings of the III International Scientific and Practical Conference "Development of the Agricultural Sector and Implementation of Scientific Research in Production", Mykolaiv, November 4-6. 2020, Mykolaiv: MNAU, 2020. P. 18-20.

17. Belov Y. V. Improving the technology of growing maize hybrids in the conditions of the Southern Steppe of Ukraine: PhD thesis: 06.01.09. Mykolaiv, 2020.

22 c.

18. Kovalenko O.A. Sugar Sorghum: Environmental and economic growing Indicators. Das intellektuelle und technologische Potenzial des XXI Jahrhunderts: Informatik, Architektur, Chemie und Pharmazie, Medizin, Landwirtschaft, Recht, Geschichte. Monografische Reihe "Europäische Wissenschaft". Buch 15. Teil 1. Karlsruhe, Germany. 2022. P.86-132. <https://doi.org/10.30890/2709-2313.2022-15-01>

19. Kovalenko O.A. Spring barley: ecologization and economic indicators of cultivation: Scientific monograph. "Modern aspects of scientific research in the context of modernization of biological and natural science education". Riga, Latvia: "Baltija Publishing", 2022. P. 77-117. DOI <https://doi.org/10.30525/978-9934-26-257-9-5>

20. Formation of photosynthetic and grain yield of spring barley (*Hordeum vulgare* L.) depend on varietal characteristics and plant growth regulators/ A. Panfilova and other. Agronomy Research. 2019. Vol. 17 (2), P. 608-620.

21. Influence of growth regulators and bacterial preparations on the productivity of spring barley in the Southern Steppe of Ukraine. Innovative technologies in crop production: materials of the II All-Ukrainian Internet conference, Kamianets-Podilskyi, May 15. 2019, / Ministry of Agrarian Policy and Food of Ukraine. Ukraine ; Podilskyi State Agrotechnical University ; Mykolaiv National Agrarian University. Kamianets-Podilskyi, 2019. P. 70-72.

22. Kovalenko O., Hekalo Y., Zborovsky D. Influence of foliar fertilization on the yield of spring barley varieties in the conditions of the NRPC of the MNAU. Proceedings of the V International Scientific and Practical Conference "Development of the agrarian sector and implementation of scientific developments in production" (Mykolaiv, October 19-21, 2022). Mykolaiv: MNAU, 2022. P.92-96. <https://dspace.mnau.edu.ua/jspui/handle/123456789/12235>.

23. Methods of State Variety Testing of Crops / Methods of Determining the Quality Indicators of Plant Products. edited by O. M. Honchar. Kyiv: Alfa, 2000. Issue 7. 150 p.

24. Methodical recommendations for conducting field experiments with cereals, legumes and fodder crops (research, accounting and observation) / [Z. B. Borisonyk, G. P. Zhemela, V. F. Kiver and others]; under the general editorship of V. S. Tsikov and G. R. Pikush Dnipropetrovsk, VNIIEK, 1983. 49 p.

25. Dospekhov B. A. Methods of field experiment: (With the basics of statistical processing of research results). [4th ed., revision and supplement]. Moscow: Kolos, 1979. 416 p.